

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
TRAINING AND PLACEMENT CELL PROJECT
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Date: 2021/12/07

ABSTRACT

TRAINING AND PLACEMENT CELL is a web based application developed in the windows platform for the training and placement department of the college in order to provide the details of its students in a database for the companies to their process of recruitment provided with a proper login.

The **TRAINING AND PLACEMENT CELL** contains all the information about the students. The system stores all the personal information of the students, like their personal details, their aggregate marks, their skill set and their technical skills that are required in the CV to be sent to a company.

The system is an online application that can be accessed throughout the organization and outside as well with proper login provided. This system can be used as an application for the TPC of the college to manage the student information with regards to placement.

This project contains all the details of the students that can be viewed by all the users (read only), but can be modified only by the student with an authorized service. By maintaining student's information, the system helps to have selections to be made easy for a company in its test for the recruitment process. The students can update their own information only. Students can search for the material required for the selection process such as aptitude, reasoning...etc and various websites for placement papers. Events happening in the college and the achievements of the student's i.e. selected students details can be viewed by all the users. So, our project provides a facility of maintaining the details of the students, and gets the requested list of candidates for the companies who would like to recruit the people based on a given query.

1.1 INTRODUCTION ABOUT THE PROJECT :

Training and Placement Cell is a total management and informative system, which provides the up-to date information of all the students in a particular college. **TPC** helps the colleges to overcome the difficulty in keeping records of hundreds and thousands of students and searching for a student eligible for recruitment criteria from the whole thing. It helps in effective and timely utilization of the hardware and the software resources.

The home page contain various links such as links to login, various services like Events happened, achievements and recruiter details etc.,. The administrator will create the users and the users will use the accounts created by administrator. When the user enters into his respective page he can update his details, and the details are to be approved by the administrator.

All the users have some common services like changing password, updating details, searching for details, checking the details, mailing to administrator, and reading the material uploaded by admin if the user is a student. Administrator has the services to add events and achievements and he can reply to the mails sent by users. He can upload materials, search for student details, and he has the right to approve the students.

1.1.1 SCOPE:

Training and Placement Cell is a total management and informative system, which provides the up-to date information of all the students in a particular college. **TPC** helps the colleges to overcome the difficulty in keeping records of hundreds and thousands of students and searching for a student eligible for recruitment criteria from the whole thing. It helps in effective and timely utilization of the hardware and the software resources.

1.1.2 PROBLEM DEFINITION

Now a day's campus placement are conducted in all colleges. Various software and other sector companies are conducting campus selections for selecting merit candidates. When campus selections are conducted the students should provide their curriculum vitae to the concern officer for attending the campus interviews. This routine process is maintained manually, like maintenance of their resumes in papers.

1.2 EXISTING SYSTEM

The earlier system is not computerized. All transactions in the system are done manually maintaining records. To make this laborious job simple the clients have to computerize the system.

The management and all the departments that have been carrying out this job using manually makes the job more complicated and tedious most of the times. So, the best way is computerize computerization of the current environment.

For example, in the earlier system placement officer has to collect student details for placements. Approving those student details takes lot of time. Placement officer and students have to consult each other directly if any information is needed. If any new company come for placements, placement officer and his staff has to search the student details and they have to find the eligible candidates for that particular company placement.

Here searching for eligible candidates takes lots of time. And some time some candidates' details may be missed.

DRAWBACKS

It takes so much time for a placement officer to collect students' details and approving the details provided by them.

- Poor communication between students and placement officer, so here intimating about new placements is a hard task.
- Students may not know about company details. Here also poor communication provides a problem.
- Candidate may not get required information if concerned TPO is not at the desk.

1.3 PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system is fully computerized, which removes all the drawbacks of existing system. Proposed system is an online application that can be accessed throughout the organization and outside as well with proper login provided. This system can be used as an application for the TPO of the college to manage the student information with regards to placement. Students logging should be able to upload their information in the form of a CV. Visitors/Company representatives logging in may also access/search any information put up by Students.

The home page contain various links such as links to login ,various services like events happened, achievements and recruiter details etc., .The administrator will create the users and the users will use the accounts created by administrator. When the user entered into his respective page he has to update his details. And the details are to be approved by the administrator.

All the users have some common services like changing password, updating details, searching for details, checking the details, mailing to administrator, and reading the material uploaded by admin if the user is a student. Administrator has to do the services like adding events, achievements and he can reply to the mails sent by users. He can upload materials, search for student details, and he has the right to approve the students.

ADVANTAGES

- Placement officer can easily collect student' details, and approve the details providedby them.
- As it is an online application, communication with placement officer is easy to students and recruiters, so here intimating about new placements very easy task.
- Students can know about company details through the details provided by Placementofficer and through the websites provided by him at *recruiters'* option.
- Here recruiters can also search for the details provided by students on the basis oftheir percentage.
- Placement officer can send required materials used for placements preparation tostudents. With this option preparation for placements becomes easy.

Detail information about system modules:

1.Administrative module:-

It allocates purchases and user details. This module can be change or modify the details.

2. Student module:- This module allocate all student details.

3. Recuruitment module: This module allocate all of student details.

4. Job module: This module allocates all job details of student.

2. REQUIREMENT ANALYSIS

2.1 FEASIBILITY STUDY

All projects are feasible – given unlimited resources and infinite time! Unfortunately, the development of computer-based system or product is more likely plagued by a scarcity of resources and difficult delivery dates. It is both necessary and prudent to evaluate the feasibility of a project at the earliest possible time. Months or years of effort, thousands or millions of dollars, and untold professional embarrassment can be averted if an ill-conceived system is recognized early in the definition phase.

2.1.1 TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY:

It is technically feasible to design the project as; the entire modules described in the modules description can be created using Front-End interaction HTML and back end database oracle.

Advantages of ORACLE

1. Oracle is a large database and several functional programs.
2. Oracle is a pure database software. In our project we maintain database, so we selected Oracle
3. It provides a set of functional programs that user can use as tools to build structures and perform tasks.
4. Oracle is highly secured software.
5. Oracle contains many tools like SQL, PL/SQL etc
6. SQL is a unified non-procedural language

2.1.2 ECONOMIC FEASIBILITY

The developing system must be justified by cost and benefit. Criteria to ensure that effort is concentrated on project, which will give best, return at the earliest. One of the factors, which affect the development of a new system, is the cost it would require.

The following are some of the important financial questions asked during preliminary investigation:

- The costs conduct a full system investigation.
- The cost of the hardware and software.
- The benefits in the form of reduced costs or fewer costly errors.

Since the system is developed as part of project work, there is no manual cost to spend for the proposed system. Also all the resources are already available, it give an indication of the system is economically possible for development.

2.1.3 OPERATIONAL FEASIBILITY

In our application front end is developed using GUI. So it is very easy to the user to enter the necessary information. But the should have user has some knowledge on using web applications before going to use our application.

2.2.1 FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENT:

ADMINISTRATIVE:

INPUT: Administrator should the valid user name and pass word.

COMPUTATION: these data are verified and saved.

OUTPUT: Administrator into admin page.

STORAGE: these details are saved in Administrator details

ADD STUDENT DETAILS:

INPUT: Enter Student id, password.

COMPUTATION: these data are verified and saved.

OUTPUT: an student details are added

STORAGE: these details are added in student details in student or student data base

RECURITER DETAILS:

Add student: add new student to the student module.

INPUT: add new student to the student module.

COMPUTATION: these data are verified and saved.

OUTPUT: New student details are added

STORAGE: these student details are added to the student information system

Add student price details:

INPUT: insert student price details

COMPUTATION: these data are verified and saved.

OUTPUT: every student price details are added when new student are add.

STORAGE: the student marks details are stored in the student data base who are passed in exams

Remove old student details:

INPUT: insert old student details.

COMPUTATION: these data are verified and saved.

OUTPUT: the old student are removed.

STORAGE: the student details are stored in the student data base

Update student details:

INPUT: insert and update student details

COMPUTATION: these details can be change or modified

OUTPUT: the student details are updated

STORAGE: these update student details are stored in student date base

2.2.2 Non-Functional Requirements:

Non-functional requirements are the constraints that must be adhered during development. They limit what resources can be used and set bounds on aspects of the software's quality.

USER INTERFACES:

The User Interface is a GUI developed using HTML.

SOFTWARE INTERFACE:

The main processing is done on the server side using apache tomcat and for the programming environment java is used, for backend database oracle is used.

PERFORMANCE REQUIREMENTS:

The product performance needs to be assessed on certain characteristics. Input: The inputs that the student gives i.e., user id and password is very important.

DESIGN CONSTRAINTS

The system we have developed is constrained by network resources.

MANPOWER REQUIREMENTS

5 members can complete this in 2 – 4 months if they work fulltime on it.

2.2.3 Environment & Technology Requirements:

- By using the HTML software
We make use of Java Swing concept and design the screen
- All the environmental variables are set.

2.2.3.1 Hardware

Specification

Processor	:	Pentium III/AMD Athlone XP
RAM	:	512 MB
Hard disk	:	1GB
FDD	:	1.44MB
Monitor	:	14 inch
Mouse		3 Button scroll
CD Drive	:	52 X
Keyboard	:	108 key

2.2.3.2 Software

Specification

Operating System	:	Windows 2000/xp /7
Languages	:	java (html ,awt and jdbc)
Front End	:	jsp(java server pages)
Platform	:	netbeans.
Backend	:	Oracle XE
Server	:	Tomcat

INTRODUCTION TO JAVA

HISTORY OF JAVA

Java language was developed by James Gosling and his team at sun micro systems and released formally in 1995. Its former name is oak. Java Development Kit 1.0 was released in 1996. to popularize java and is freely available on Internet.

Overview of Java

Java is loosely based on C++ syntax, and is men at to be Object-Oriented Structure of java is midway between an interpreted and a compiled language . java programs are compiled by the java compiler into Byte Codes which are secure and portable across different platforms . these byte codes are essentially instructions encapsulated in single type, to what is known as a java virtual machine (JVM) which resides in standard browser.

Jvm verifies these byte codes when downloaded by the browser for integrity. Jvms available for almost all OS. JVM converts these byte codes into machine specific instructions at runtime.

FEATURES OF JAVA

- Java is object-oriented language and supports encapsulation, inheritance, polymorphism and dynamic binding , but does not support multiple inheritance. everything in java is an object except some primitive datatypes .
- java is portable architecture neutral that is java programs once compiled can be executed on any machine that is enabled.
- JAVA is distributed in its approach and used for internet programming.
- Java is robust, secured, high performing and dynamic in nature.
- Java supports multithreading. There for different parts of the program can be executed at the same time

JAVA AND INTERNET

Java is strongly associated with internet and known as internet programming language. Internet users can use java to create applet programs and run them locally using java enabled browser search as hot java. Applets can be downloaded from remote machine via internet and run it on local machine .

JAVA AND WORLD WIDE WEB

World wide web is an open ended information retrieval system designed to be used in the distributed environment. This system contains web pages that provide both information and controls. We can navigate to a new web page in any direction. This is made possible with HTML java was meant to be used in distributed environment such as internet. So java could be easily incorporated into the web system and is capable of supporting animation graphics, games and other special effect. The web has become more dynamic and interactive with support of java. We can run a java program on remote machine over internet with the support of web .

JAVA ENVIRONMENT

Java environment includes a large no. of tools which are part of the system known as java development kit (JDK) and hundreds of classes, methods, and interfaces grouped into packages forms part of java standard library(JSL).

JAVA ARCHITECTURE

Java architecture provides a portable , robust , high performing environment for development. Java provides portability by compiling the byte codes for the java virtual machine which are then interpreted on each platform by the runtime environment . java also provides stringent compile and runtime checking and automatic memory management in order to ensure solid code

JAVA VIRTUAL MACHINE

When we compile the code, java compiler creates machine code (byte code) for a hypothetical machine called java virtual machine (jvm). The jvm will execute the byte code and overcomes the issue of portability . the code is written and compile for one machine and interpreted all other machines . this machine is called java virtual machine .

PARADIGM OF JAVA

- Dynamic down loading applets(small application programs);
- Elimination of flatware phenomenon that is providing those features of a product that user needs at a time. The remaining features of a product can remain in the server.
- Changing economic model of the software
- Up-to-date software availability
- Supports network entire computing
- Supports CORBA & DCOM

ABOUT HTML

HTML (hyper text markup language) is a language used to create hyper text documents that have hyper links embedded in them .it consists of tags embedded in the textof a document with HTML. We can build web pages or web document s. it is basically a formatting language and not a programming language. The browser reading the document interprets mark up tags to help format the document for subsequent display to a reader. HTML is a language for describing structured documents. HTML is a platform independent. WWW (world wide web) pages are written using HTML. HTML tags control in part the representation of the WWW page when view with web browser. The browser interprets HTML tags in the web document and displays it. Different browsers show data differently. Examples of browsers used to be web pages include:

- Netscape
- Internet Explorer

JAVA SCRIPT

Java script is a general purpose, prototype based, object oriented scripting language developed jointly by sun and netscape and is meant for the WWW. it is designed to be embedded in diverse applications and systems , without consuming much memory . java script borrows most of its syntax from java but also inherits from awk and perl, with some indirect influence from self in its object prototype system.

Java scripts dynamically typed that is programs do not declare variable types, and the type of variable is unrestricted and can change at runtime .source can be generated at run time and evaluated against an arbitrary scope. Typical implementations compile by translating source into a specified byte code format, to check syntax and source consistency. Note that the availability to generate and interpret programs at runtime implies the presence of a compiler at runtime.

Java script is a high level scripting language that does not depend on or expose particular machine representations or operating system services. It provides automatic storage management, typically using a garbage collector.

FEATURES:

- Java script is embedded into HTML documents and is executed with in them.
- Java script is browser dependent
- Javascript is an interpreted languaged that can be interpreted by the browser at run time.
- Java script is loosely typed language
- Java script is an object based language.
- Java script is an Eent-Driven language and supports event handlers to specify the functionality of a button.

ADVANTAGES

1. javascript provides means to contain multi frame windows for presentation of the web.
2. javascript provides basic data validation before it is sent to the server. Eg : login and password checking or whether the values entered are correct or whether all fields in a form are filled and reduced network traffic
- 3 .it creates interactive forms and client side lookup tables

INTRODUCTION TO JDBC

JDBC (Java Database connectivity) is a front-end tool for connecting to a server to ODBC in that respect, however JDBC can connect only java client and it uses ODBC for the connectivity. JDBC is essentially a low-level API since any data manipulation, storage and retrieval has to be done by the program itself. Some tools, which provide a higher-level abstraction, are expected shortly. The next question that needs to be answered is why we need JDBC, once we have ODBC on hand. We can use the same ODBC to connect the entire database and ODBC is a proven technology. Problem for doing this is ODBC gives a 'c' language API, which uses pointers extensively. Since java does not have any pointers and is object-oriented sun Microsystems, inventor of java developed to suit its needs.

Requirements to use JDBC:

To use JDBC you need a basic knowledge of databases and SQL. A part from this you need the jdk1.1 (Java Development Kit 1.1 available javasoft's website) or a version of Java since jdk1.1 and above come bundled with JDBC software. After that you need to have a back-end database engine for which a JDBC driver is available. When JDBC drivers are not available JDBC-ODBC bridge drivers are used to access the database through ODBC. Back-end is not needed when JDBC driver is capable of storing and retrieving the data itself, or if JDBC-ODBC Bridge and the ODBC driver can be used to store and retrieve the information.

DATABASE MODELS

JDBC and accessing the database through applets and JDBC API via an intermediate server resulted in a new type of database model which is different from the client-server model. Based on number of intermediate server through the request should go it is named as single tier, two tier and multi tier architecture.

Single Tier

In a single tier the server and client are the same in the sense that a client program that needs information (client) and the source of this type of architecture is also possible in java, in case flat files are used to store the data. However this is useful only in case of small applications. The advantage with this is the simplicity and portability of the application developed.

Two Tier (client-server)

In two tier architecture the database resides in one machine and client in different machine they are connected through the network. In this type of architecture a database management takes control of the database and provides access to clients in a network. This software bundle is also called as the server. Software in different machines, requesting for information are called as the clients

JDBC binary code end in many cases database client code must be loaded on each client machine that uses this driver. As a result, this kind of driver is most appropriate on a corporate network where client installations are not major problem, or for application server code written in java in a 3-tier architecture.

2. NATIVE API PARTLY-JAVA DRIVER

This kind of driver converts JDBC calls into calls on the client API for oracle Sybase, Informix, DB2, or other DBMS. Note that, like the bridge driver, this style of driver requires that some binary code be loaded on each client machine.

3. JDBC-NET ALL-JAVA DRIVER

This driver translates JDBC calls into a DBMS independent net protocol, which is then translated, to a DBMS protocol by a server. This net server middle-ware is able to connect its all java clients to many different databases. The Specific protocol used depends on the vendor. In general, this most flexible JDBC alternative. It is likely that all vendors of this solution will provide products suitable for intranet use.

4. NATIVE PROTOCOL ALL-JAVA DRIVER

This kind of driver converts JDBC calls into the network protocol used by DBMS directory. This allows a direct call from the client machine to the DBMS server that is practical solution for intranet access. Since many of these protocols are proprietary, the database vendors themselves will be the primary source. Several database vendors have these in progress. Eventually, we expect that driver categories 3 and 4 will be the preferred way to access databases from JDBC. Driver categories one and two are interim solutions where direct all java drivers are not yet available. Category 4 is in some sense the ideal; however, there are many cases where category 3 may be preferable: eg: -where a thin DBMS-independent client is desired, or if a DBMS –independent protocol is standardized and implemented directly by many DBMS vendors.

Result set enhancements

The JDBC 1.0 API provided result sets that had the ability to scroll in a forward direction only. Scrollable result sets allow for more flexibility in the processing of results by providing both forward and backward movement through their contents. In addition, scrollable result sets allow for relative and absolute positioning. **For example, it's possible** to move to the fourth row in a scrollable result set directly, or to move directly to the third row following the current row, provided the row exists. The JDBC API allows result sets to be directly updatable, as well.

Batch updates

The batch update feature allows an application to submit multiple update statements(insert/update/delete) in a single request to the database. This can provide a dramatic increase in performance when a large number of update statements need to be executed.

Advanced data types

Increased support for storing persistent Java programming language objects (Java objects)and a mapping for SQL99 data types such as binary large objects, and structured types, has been added to the JDBC API. An application may also customize the mapping of SQL99 structured types into Java programming language classes.

What is a Servlet?

Servlets are modules that extend request/response-oriented servers, such as Java-enabled web servers. For example, a servlet might be responsible for taking data in an HTML order-entry form and applying the business logic used to update a company's order database.

Servlets are to servers what applets are to browsers. Unlike applets, however, servlets have no graphical user interface. Servlets can be embedded in many different servers because the servlet API, which you use to write servlets, assumes nothing about the server's environment or protocol. Servlets have become most widely used within HTTP servers; many web servers support the Servlet API.

The Servlet Interface

The central abstraction in the Servlet API is the Servlet interface. All servlets implement this interface, either directly or, more commonly, by extending a class that implements it such as `HttpServlet`.

The Servlet interface declares, but does not implement, methods that manage the servlet and its communications with clients. Servlet writers provide some or all of these methods when developing a servlet.

A Simple Servlet

The following class completely defines a servlet:

```
public class SimpleServlet extends HttpServlet {
    /**
     * Handle the HTTP GET method by building a simple web
     * page. */
    public void doGet (HttpServletRequest request, HttpServletResponse response)
        throws ServletException, IOException
    {
        PrintWriterStringout;title"Simple
        Servlet Output";

        // set content type and other response header fields first
        response.setContentType("text/html");
        / then write the data of the response
        System.out = response.getWriter();
        System.out.println("<HTML><HEAD><TITLE>");
        System.out.println(title);
        System.out.println("</TITLE></HEAD><BODY>");
        System.out.println("<H1>" + title + "</H1>");
        System.out.println("<P>This is output from SimpleServlet.");
        System.out.println("</BODY></HTML>");
        System.out.close();

        }

    }
```

1. Servlet Lifecycle

Each servlet has the same life cycle:

- A server loads and initializes the servlet
- The servlet handles zero or more client requests
- The server removes the servlet

Initializing a Servlet

When a server loads a servlet, the server runs the servlet's init method. Initialization completes before client requests are handled and before the servlet is destroyed. Even though most servlets are run in multi-threaded servers, servlets have no concurrency issues during servlet initialization. The server calls the init method once, when the server loads the servlet, and will not call the init method again unless the server is reloading the servlet. The server can not reload a servlet until after the server has destroyed the servlet by calling the destroy method.

The init Method

The init method provided by the HttpServlet class initializes the servlet and logs the initialization. To do initialization specific to your servlet, override the init() method following these rules:

- If an initialization error occurs that renders the servlet incapable of handling client requests, throw an Unavailable Exception. An example of this type of error is the inability to establish a required network connection.

Session Endurance

After the user has been idle for more than a certain period of time (30 minutes by default), the user's session becomes invalid, and the corresponding Session object is destroyed.

A session is a set of requests originating from the same browser, going to the same server, bounded by a period of time. Loosely speaking, a session corresponds to a single *sitting* of a single anonymous user (anonymous because no explicit login or authentication is required to participate in session tracking).

Functions

Functions are bet declared between the <Head> tag of HTML page. Functions are called by user-initiated events. Seems reasonable to keep the functions between the <Head> tags. They are loaded first before a user can do anything that might call a function. Scripts can be placed between inside comment fields to ensure that older browser do not display the script itself.

```
<html>
<head>
<script language="JavaScript">function pushbutton () {alert ("Hello!");
</script>
</head>
<body>
<form>
<input type="button" name="Button1" value="push me" onclick="pushbutton ()">
</form>
</body>
</html>
```

If we want to test this one immediately and you are using a Java Script enabled browser then please go ahead and push the button. This script will create a button and when you press it a window will pop up saying "hello!". In fact we have a lot of possibilities just by adding functions to our scripts. The common browsers transmit the form information by either method: here's the complete tag including the GET transmission method attribute for the previous form

ORACLE

INTRODUCTION:

Oracle is a relational database management system, which organizes data in the form of tables. Oracle is one of many database servers based on RDBMS model, which manages a sea of data that attends three specific things-data structures, data integrity and data manipulation. With oracle cooperative server technology we can realize the benefits of open, relational systems for all the applications. Oracle makes efficient use of all systems resources, on all hardware architecture; to deliver unmatched performance, price performance and scalability. Any DBMS to be called as RDBMS has to satisfy Dr.E.F.Codd's rules.

DISTINCT FEATURES OF ORACLE:

➤ **ORACLE IS PORTABLE:**

The Oracle RDBMS is available on wide range of platforms ranging from PCs to super computers and as a multi user loadable module for Novel NetWare, if you develop application on system you can run the same application on other systems without any modifications.

➤ **ORACLE IS COMPATIBLE:**

Oracle commands can be used for communicating with IBM DB2 mainframe RDBMS that is different from Oracle, that is Oracle compatible with DB2. Oracle RDBMS is a high performance fault tolerant DBMS, which is specially designed for online transaction processing and for handling large database applications

➤ **MULTITHREADED SERVER ARCHITECTURE:**

Oracle adaptable multithreaded server architecture delivers scalable high performance for very large number of users on all hardware architecture including symmetric multiprocessors (sumps) and loosely coupled multiprocessors. Performance is achieved by eliminating CPU, I/O, memory and operating system bottlenecks and by optimizing the Oracle DBMS server code to eliminate all internal bottlenecks.

FEATURES OF ORACLE:

Most popular RDBMS in the market because of its ease of use

- Client/server architecture.
- Data independence.
- Ensuring data integrity and data security.
- Managing data concurrency.
- Parallel processing support for speed up data entry and online transaction processing used for applications.
- DB procedures, functions and packages.

ORACLE SUPPORTS THE FOLLOWING CODD'S RULES:

Rule 1: Information Rule (Representation of information)-YES.

Rule 2 : Guaranteed Access-YES.

Rule 3: Systematic treatment of Null values-YES.

Rule 4: Dynamic on-line catalog-based Relational Model-YES.

Rule 5: Comprehensive data sub language-YES.

Rule 6: View Updating-PARTIAL.

Rule 7: High-level Update, Insert and Delete-YES.

Rule 8: Physical data Independence-PARTIAL.

Rule 9: Logical data Independence-PARTIAL.

Rule 10: Integrity Independence-PARTIAL.

Rule 11: Distributed Independence-YES.

Rule 12: Non-subversion-YES.

Java is a small, simple, safe, object oriented, interpreted or dynamically optimized, byte coded, architectural, garbage collected, multithreaded programming language with a strongly typed exception-handling for writing distributed and dynamically extensible programs. Java is an object oriented programming language. Java is a high-level, thirdgeneration language like C, FORTRAN, Small talk, Pearl and many others. You can use java to write computer applications that crunch numbers, process words, play games, store data or do any of the thousands of other things computer software can do.

Special programs called applets that can be downloaded from the internet and played safely within a web browser. Java a supports this application and the follow features make it one of the best programming languages.

- It is simple and object oriented
- It helps to create user friendly interfaces.
- It is very dynamic.
- It supports multithreading.
- It is platform independent
- It is highly secure and robust.
- It supports internet programming

Java is a programming language originally developed by Sun Microsystems and released in 1995 as a core component of Sun's Java platform. The language derives much of its syntax from C and C++ but has a simpler object model and fewer low-level facilities. Java applications are typically compiled to byte code which can run on any Java virtual machine (JVM) regardless of computer architecture.

The original and reference implementation Java compilers, virtual machines, and class libraries were developed by Sun from 1995. As of May 2007, in compliance with the specifications of the Java Community Process, Sun made available most of their Java technologies as free software under the GNU General Public License

The Java language was created by James Gosling in June 1991 for use in a set top box project. The language was initially called *Oak*, after an oak tree that stood outside Gosling's office - and also went by the name *Green* - and ended up later being renamed to *Java*, from a list of random words. Gosling's goals were to implement a virtual machine and a language that had a familiar C/C++ style of notation.

Primary goals

There were five primary goals in the creation of the Java language:

- ❖ It should use the object-oriented programming methodology.
- ❖ It should allow the same program to be executed on multiple operating systems.
- ❖ It should contain built-in support for using computer networks.
- ❖ It should be designed to execute code from remote sources securely.
- ❖ It should be easy to use by selecting what were considered the good parts of other object-oriented languages.

The *Java platform* is the name for a bundle of related programs, or platform, from Sun which allow for developing and running programs written in the Java programming language. The platform is not specific to any one processor or operating system, but rather an execution engine (called a virtual machine) and a compiler with a set of standard libraries which are implemented for various hardware and operating systems so that Java programs can run identically on all of them. Different "editions" of the platform are available, including:

- ❖ Java ME (Micro Edition): Specifies several different sets of libraries (known as profiles) for devices which are sufficiently limited that supplying the full set of Java libraries would take up unacceptably large amounts of storage.
- ❖ Java SE (Standard Edition): For general purpose use on desktop PCs, servers and similar devices.
- ❖ Java EE (Enterprise Edition): Java SE plus various APIs useful for multi-tier client-server enterprise applications.

The Java Platform consists of several programs, each of which provides a distinct portion of its overall capabilities. For example, the Java compiler, which converts Java source code into Java bytecode (an intermediate language for the Java Virtual Machine (JVM)), is provided as part of the Java Development Kit (JDK). The sophisticated Java Runtime Environment (JRE), complementing the JVM with a just-in-time (JIT) compiler, converts intermediate bytecode into native machine code on the fly. Also supplied are extensive libraries (pre-compiled into Java bytecode) containing reusable code, as well as numerous ways for Java applications to be deployed, including being embedded in a web page as an applet. There are several other components, some available only in certain editions.

3. DESIGN

3.1. SYSTEM DESIGN:

Design is The Diagrammatical representation of the Project. It is the first step to moving from the problem domain towards the solution domain. It is essentially the bridge between requirements specification and the final solution for satisfying the requirements.

The design for software systems often has two levels. At the first level the focus is on deciding which modules are needed for the system, the specifications of these modules, and how the modules should be interconnected. This is what is called System design or top- level design.

In the second level, the internal design of the modules or how the specifications of the module can be satisfied is decided upon. This design level is often called The Detailed design or Logical design. The system design has a major impact on the testability and modifiability of a system.

System design can be viewed from either technical or project management perspective. From the technical point of view, design is comprised of four activities

- architectural design
- data structure design
- interface design
- Procedural design.

3.1.1 Introduction to Uml Diagrams:

UML is for diagrammatic notations i.e visualizing, specifying, constructing and documenting the components of software and non software systems.

UML notations are the most important elements in modeling. Efficient and appropriate use of notations is very important for making a complete and meaningful model.

UML is specifically constructed through two different domains they are:

- UML Analysis modeling: It is focuses on the user model and structural model views of the system.
- UML design modeling: It is focuses on the behavioral modeling, implementation modeling and environmental model views.

Use Case:

A Use case is a set of scenario that describes an interaction between user and a system. A Use case diagram displays the relationship among Actors and Use cases. There are two main components of Use case diagrams are:

- Use cases Functions
- Actors-User

Actor:

An actor can be defined as some internal or external entity that interacts with the system. It could be a user or another system. The actor "uses" the use case to complete a task. *System Administrator, Authentication System, Student, Parent, Faculty* and *Web Client* are all examples of actors.

Interface Notation:

Interface is represented by a circle. It has a name which is generally written below the circle. Interface is used to describe functionality without implementation. When a class implements the interface it also implements the functionality as per the requirement.

Collaboration Notation:

Collaboration is represented by a dotted ellipse. It has a name written inside the ellipse. Collaboration represents responsibilities. Generally responsibilities are in a group.

Additional components can be used for clarification

Initial State Notation:

Initial state is defined to show the start of a process. The usage of Initial State Notation is to show the starting point of a process

Final State Notation:

Final state is used to show the end of a process. This notation is also used in almost all diagrams to describe the end. The usage of Final State Notation is to show the termination point of a process.

Package Notation:

Package notation is used to wrap the components of a system.

Additional Components can be used for clarification

Note Notation:

This notation is used to provide necessary information of a system.

Relationships:

A model is not complete unless the relationships between elements are described properly. The *Relationship* gives a proper meaning to an UML model. Following are the different types of relationships available in UML.

- Dependency
- Association
- Generalization
- Extensibility

Dependency Notation:

Dependency describes the dependent elements and the direction of dependency. Dependency is represented by a dotted arrow. The arrow head represents the independent element and the other end the dependent element. Dependency is used to represent dependency between two elements of a system.

Association:

The **association** is the link that is drawn between an actor and a use case. It indicates which actors interact with the system to complete the various tasks.

Association is represented by a dotted line with (without) arrows on both sides. The two ends represent two associated elements. The multiplicity is also mentioned at the ends (1, * etc) to show how many objects are associated.

Generalization of Notation:

Generalization describes the inheritance relationship of the object oriented world. It is parent and child relationship.

Generalization is represented by an arrow with hollow arrow head. One end represents the parent element and the other end child element.

Extensibility Notation:

All the languages have some mechanism to extend its capabilities like syntax, semantics etc. UML is also having the following mechanisms to provide extensibility features.

Stereotypes (Represents new elements)

Tagged values (Represents new attributes)

Constraints (Represents the boundaries)

Extensibility notations are used to enhance the power of the language. It is basically additional elements used to represent some extra behavior of the system. These extra behaviors are not covered by the standard available notations.

3.1.2.1 Scenarios:

System Design is one of the tasking sections of the Programming. In this section of the project many previews are going to be seen and we are gradually getting close to the new system. System design is a transition from a user-oriented document to a document oriented to programmers or database personnel.

3.12.1 USE CASES DIAGRAM:

Fig: use cases diagram for adimin, student, recruite

3.1.2.2 CLASS DIAGRAM:

5. SEQUENCE DIAGRAMS:

FOR ADMIN:

Student or students are added to the cell

Recrutier added to the cell

Students and recrutier are approved

Materials are uploaded to the cell

Admin can mail to the students and recurtier`

FOR STUDENT:

student

login

Student can mail to the admin

Recruiter can obtain the student details

Recruiter can mail to the admin

Recruiter can change his password

ACTIVITY DIAGRAMS:

FOR ADMIN :

Act

FOR USER :

Activa

COLLABORATION DIAGRAMS:

Tables

S no	FIELD NAME	Type
1	Name	VARCHAR2(20)
2	CCODE	VARCHAR2(20)
3	CNAME	VARCHAR2(20)
4	EMPID	VARCHAR2(20)
5	BRANCHES	VARCHAR2(20)
6	NOS	VARCHAR2(20)
7	PHONE	NUMBER(20)
8	EMAIL	VARCHAR2(20)
9	STATE	VARCHAR2(20)
10	LOCATIONNAME	VARCHAR2(20)
11	MAXNO OFRETAILERS	VARCHAR2(20)
12	COUNTRY	VARCHAR2(20)

RECRUITER:

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2	RNAME	Varchar2(30)
3	PHONE	NUMBER(20)
4	EMAIL	Varchar2(20)
5	HOUSE-No	VARCHAR2(20)
6	STREET	VARCHAR2(20)
7	CITY	VARCHAR2(20)
8	COUNTRY	VARCHAR2(20)
9	RNAME	NUMBER2(10)

LOGIN:

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2	Password	Varchar2(30)
3	Type of User	Varchar2(30)

MATERIAL:

S no	FIELD NAME	Type
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2	MATNAME	Varchar2(30)

HALLTICKET:

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2	Company Id	Varchar2(30)

EVENT:

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SOURCE CODE

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SCREENS

HOME PAGE:

EVENTS

The screenshot shows a web application interface for the 'TRAINING AND PLACEMENT CELL'. The header features a logo with stylized leaves and the text 'TRAINING AND PLACEMENT CELL' with the tagline 'we lay the steps for your future.....'. A navigation menu includes 'home', 'events', 'recruiters', 'achievements', and 'aboutus'. On the left, there is a 'Login' section with input fields for 'Login ID:' and 'Password:', a 'Sign In' button with a user icon, and a 'ForgotPassword' link. The main content area is titled 'Events:' and contains a table with the following data:

Events posted on	Event
2007-04-16 09:30:43	subject
2007-04-11 11:05:54	subject
2007-04-09 16:10:51	subject

RECRUITERS PAGE:

TRAINING AND PLACEMENT CELL
we lay the steps for your future.....

home | events | **recruiters** | achievements | aboutus

Login

Login ID:

Password:

Sign In

[ForgotPassword](#)

<i>CompanyName</i>	<i>Website</i>
wipro	www.wipro.com
infosys	www.infosys.com
TCS	www.tcs.com
canbay	www.canbay.com

ADMINISTRATOR LOGIN:

The screenshot displays the website for the Training and Placement Cell. At the top left is a logo consisting of stylized blue and yellow leaves. To its right, the text "TRAINING AND PLACEMENT CELL" is written in blue, with the tagline "we lay the steps for your future....." in red below it. A navigation bar contains links for "home", "events", "recruiters", "achievements", and "aboutus". On the left side, there is a "Login" section with a "Login ID:" field containing "admin", a "Password:" field with masked characters, and a "Sign In" button with a person icon. The main content area features three images: a handshake, a modern building, and a group of people in a meeting. Below these images is a paragraph of text describing the system's purpose.

TRAINING AND PLACEMENT CELL
we lay the steps for your future.....

home events recruiters achievements aboutus

Login

Login ID: admin

Password: ●●●●●●

Sign In

The Training and Placement Cell provides the details of students of a college for the companies to their process of recruitment provided with a proper login. The system stores all the personal information of the students, like their personal details, aggregate of marks, their skill set and their personal skills that are required in the CV to be sent to a company. It contains details of the students that can be viewed by all the students (read only), but can be modified by only the student with an authorized service. Administrator maintains students information & the system helps to have selections to be made easy.

ADMIN ADD STUDENT:

we lay the steps for your future.....

home events recruiters achievements aboutus logout

Add Student:

To enter single student:

Hall Ticket No

To enter multiple students:

From lno: To lno:

Password

UpdateDetails
UpdateStatistics
AddStudent
AddRecruiter
AddEvent
Approve
StudentDetails
UploadMaterial
Mailing
ChangePassword

ADMIN ADD COMPANY:

The screenshot shows a web application interface for the Training and Placement Cell. At the top left is a logo with a stylized figure and the text 'TRAINING AND PLACEMENT CELL' and the tagline 'we lay the steps for your future.....'. A navigation menu includes 'home', 'events', 'recruiters', 'achievements', 'aboutus', and 'logout'. On the left side, there is a vertical menu with buttons for 'UpdateDetails', 'UpdateStatistics', 'AddStudent', 'AddRecruiter', 'AddEvent', 'Approve', 'StudentDetails', 'UploadMaterial', and 'Mailing'. The main content area is titled 'Add Company:' and contains a form with two input fields: 'Company Name' (containing 'infotech') and 'Password' (containing 'infotech'). An 'Add' button is positioned below the password field.

TRAINING AND PLACEMENT CELL
we lay the steps for your future.....

home events recruiters achievements aboutus logout

Add Company:

UpdateDetails
UpdateStatistics
AddStudent
AddRecruiter
AddEvent
Approve
StudentDetails
UploadMaterial
Mailing

Company Name infotech
Password infotech
Add

ADMIN ADD EVENT:

TRAINING AND PLACEMENT CELL
we lay the steps for your future.....

home events recruiters achievements aboutus logout

Add Event:

subject:

Add the event here...

ADD

[View Events](#)

UpdateDetails
UpdateStatistics
AddStudent
AddRecruiter
AddEvent
Approve
StudentDetails
UploadMaterial
Mailing

ADMIN ADDED EVENTS:

ADMIN APPROVAL:

we lay the steps for your future.....

home events recruiters achievements aboutus logout

<input type="checkbox"/>	03761A0550	0	0	0	0	0
<input type="checkbox"/>	03761A0551	0	0	0	0	0
<input type="checkbox"/>	03761A0552	0	0	0	0	0
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<input type="checkbox"/>	03761A0599	0	0	0	0	0
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Approve

ADMIN STUDENT DETAILS:

TRAINING AND PLACEMENT CELL
we lay the steps for your future.....

home events recruiters achievements aboutus logout

Student Details :

Total no of students... 6

Sno	Student Name	HallTicket No
1	Gopinath	03761A0512 CV
2	Archana	03761A0517 CV
3	Samatha	03761A0535 CV
4	Srujana	03761A0599 CV
5	RatnaKumari	03761A0401 CV
6	srujana	03681A0599 CV

UpdateDetails
UpdateStatistics
AddStudent
AddRecruiter
AddEvent
Approve
StudentDetails
UploadMaterial
Mailing

ADMIN EMAIL:

The screenshot displays the 'ADMIN EMAIL' interface for the Training and Placement Cell. At the top left is the organization's logo, a stylized leaf design, followed by the text 'TRAINING AND PLACEMENT CELL' and the tagline 'we lay the steps for your future.....'. A navigation bar contains links for 'home', 'events', 'recruiters', 'achievements', 'aboutus', and 'logout'. On the left side, a vertical menu lists administrative actions: 'UpdateDetails', 'UpdateStatistics', 'AddStudent', 'AddRecruiter', 'AddEvent', 'Approve', 'StudentDetails', 'UploadMaterial', and 'Mailing'. The main content area features a central heading 'Administrartor Mailing' (sic) with a wooden signpost icon that reads 'E-MAIL'. To the right, there are three primary email management options: 'Inbox' with an 'e mail' icon, 'Composemail' with an icon of a hand writing, and 'Sentitens' (sic) with a paper airplane icon.

5. TESTING

5.1 INTRODUCTION TO TESTING:

Software Testing is the process of executing software in a controlled manner, in order to answer the question - Does the software behave as specified?. Software testing is often used in association with the terms verification and validation. Validation is the checking or testing of student, includes software, for conformance and consistency with an associated specification. Software testing is just one kind of verification, which also uses techniques such as reviews, analysis, inspections, and walkthroughs. Validation is the process of checking that what has been specified is what the user actually wanted.

sValidation :Are we doing the right job?

Verification :Are we doing the job right?

Software testing should not be confused with debugging. Debugging is the process of analyzing and localizing bugs when software does not behave as expected. Although the identification of some bugs will be obvious from playing with the software, a methodical approach to software testing is a much more thorough means for identifying bugs. Debugging is therefore an activity which supports testing, but cannot replace testing.

Other activities which are often associated with software testing are static analysis and dynamic analysis. Static analysis investigates the source code of software, looking for problems and gathering metrics without actually executing the code. Dynamic analysis looks at the behavior of software while it is executing, to provide information such as execution traces, timing profiles, and test coverage information. Testing is a set of activity that can be planned in advanced and conducted systematically. Testing begins at the module level and work towards the integration of entire computers based system. Nothing is complete without testing, as it vital success of the system testing objectives, there are several rules that can serve as testing objectives. They are

- ❖ Testing is a process of executing a program with the intend of finding an error.
- ❖ A good test case is one that has high possibility of finding an undiscovered error.
- ❖ A successful test is one that uncovers an undiscovered error.

If a testing is conducted successfully according to the objectives as stated above, it would uncover errors in the software also testing demonstrate that the software function appear to be working according to the specification, that performance requirement appear to have been met.

There are three ways to test program.

- For correctness
- For implementation efficiency
- For computational complexity

5.2 TEST S PLAN

A test plan implies a series of desired course of action to be followed in accomplishing various testing methods. The Test Plan acts as a blue print for the action that is to be followed. The software engineers create a computer program, its documentation and related data structures. The software developers is always responsible for testing the individual units of the programs, ensuring that each performs the function for which it was designed. There is an independent test group (ITG) which is to remove the inherent problems associated with letting the builder to test the thing that has been built. The specific objectives of testing should be stated in

measurable terms. So that the mean time to failure, the cost to find and fix the defects, remaining defect density or frequency of occurrence and test work-hours per regression test all should be stated within the test plan.

The levels of testing include:

- ❖ Unit testing
- ❖ Integration Testing
- ❖ Data validation Testing
- ❖ Output Testing

Unit Testing:

Unit testing focuses verification effort on the smallest unit of software design – the software component or module. Using the component level design description as a guide, important control paths are tested to uncover errors within the boundary of the module. The relative complexity of tests and uncovered scope established for unit testing.

The unit testing is white-box oriented, and step can be conducted in parallel for multiple components. The modular interface is tested to ensure that information properly flows into and out of the program unit under test. The local data structure is examined to ensure that data stored temporarily maintains its integrity during all steps in an algorithm's execution. Boundary conditions are tested to ensure that all statements in a module have been executed at least once. Finally, all error handling paths are tested.

Integration Testing:

Integration testing is systematic technique for constructing the program structure while at the same time conducting tests to uncover errors associated with interfacing. The objective is to take unit tested components and build a program structure that has been dictated by design. The entire program is tested as whole. Correction is difficult because isolation of causes is complicated by vast expanse of entire program. Once these errors are corrected, new ones appear and the process continues in a seemingly endless loop.

After unit testing in Sell-Soft System all the modules were integrated to test for any inconsistencies in the interfaces. Moreover differences in program structures were removed and a unique program structure was evolved.

Validation Testing Or System Testing:

This is the final step in testing. In this the entire system was tested as a whole with all forms, code, modules and class modules. This form of testing is popularly known as Black Box testing or System tests.

Black Box testing method focuses on the functional requirements of the software. That is, Black Box testing enables the software engineer to derive sets of input conditions that will fully exercise all functional requirements for a program.

Black Box testing attempts to find errors in the following categories; incorrect or missing functions, interface errors, errors in data structures or external data access, performance errors and initialization errors and termination errors

Output Testing Or User Acceptance Testing:

The system considered is tested for **user acceptance; here it should satisfy the firm's need. The software should keep** in touch with perspective system; user at the time of developing and making changes whenever required. This done with respect to the following points

- Input Screen Designs,
- Output Screen Designs,
- Online message to guide the user and the like.

The above testing is done taking various kinds of test data. Preparation of test data plays a vital role in the system testing. After preparing the test data, the system under study is tested using that test data. While testing the system by which test data errors are again uncovered and corrected by using above testing steps and corrections are also noted for future use.

Validation Checking:

At the culmination of integration testing, software is completely assembled as a package; interfacing errors have been uncovered and corrected, and a final series of software test-validation checks may begin. Validation can be defined in many ways, but a simple definition (Albeit Harsh) is that validation succeeds when software functions in a manner that can be reasonably expected by a customer. Software validation is achieved through a series of black-box tests to be conducted and a test procedure defines specific test cases that will be used in attempt to uncover errors in conformity with requirements. Both the plan and procedure are designed to ensure that all functional requirements are satisfied; all performance requirements are achieved; documentation is correct and human –Engineered and other requirements are met.

CONCLUSION

Presently we designed our Training & Placement Cell to be very User Friendly. Many features are enhanced to the present Training & Placement Cell. With this Training & Placement Cell most of the TPO's time is saved. The features of the system can be further enhanced in many ways.

The documentation that has enclosed can enable even a person with minimum knowledge to understand it well.

PERFORMANCE:

Training & Placement Cell which is developed in JSP technology is a versatile product and is platform independent. The features provided by the Training & Placement Cell makes it one of an interactive online platform for Placements.

ENHANCEMENTS:

1. Admin module to be developed, there by automating the services of the Admin resulting in continuous flow of records from database.
2. Conducting mock tests is to be added

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